

Heating of the lower solar atmosphere by monochromatic torsional Alfvén waves

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ABSTRACT

Context. We present a new insight into the dynamics of torsional Alfvén waves in the partially-ionized lower solar atmosphere.

Aims. We aim to study, by means of numerical simulations, the propagation, attenuation and dissipation of Alfvén waves and to determine their contribution to photospheric and chromospheric plasma heating.

Methods. We numerically solve the two-fluid equations in three-dimensional (3D) Cartesian geometry. We implement a magnetic flux-tube rooted in the solar photosphere and expanding into the chromosphere above it. Alfvén waves are directly generated by a monochromatic driver operating at the bottom of the photosphere with a wave period of 30 s.

Results. Due to ion-neutral collisions, the Alfvén waves experience strong damping in the photosphere. With the steep gradients in all plasma quantities, they drive magneto-acoustic waves in the higher atmospheric layers through the ponderomotive force. As ion-neutral drift is the largest in the chromosphere, the energy carried by these waves is thermalized, and the plasma temperature rises. At the photospheric level the temperature remains essentially unchanged.

Conclusions. In comparison to the 2.5D case that is discussed in the literature, the wave damping is

significantly weaker and torsional Alfvén waves deposit less energy than their 2.5D analogues. As a result, the energy transfer to the upper atmospheric layers via driven magneto-acoustic waves is greater and this energy is deposited there. We infer that torsional Alfvén waves are able to indirectly heat the solar chromosphere.

Key words. Sun: activity - Sun: photosphere - Sun: chromosphere - Sun: transition region - methods: numerical

1. Introduction

To understand a multitude of physical processes occurring on the Sun, one has to know how the dynamics of the solar plasma is determined by the solar magnetic field. One of the omnipresent magnetic structures of the quiet Sun are magnetic flux-tubes. Observed usually in the chromosphere (e.g., Hansteen et al. 2006; De Pontieu et al. 2007; Rouppe van der Voort et al. 2009; Kuridze et al. 2015; Srivastava et al. 2017) and rooted in the photosphere in between granules, they are prone to highly turbulent motions associated with the solar granulation. The latter is an efficient source of waves propagating into the solar atmosphere, some of which were interpreted as magnetohydrodynamic-gravity waves (e.g., Musielak & Ulmschneider 2001). Recent observations revealed a diversity of waves in the solar atmosphere and demonstrated also, that some of these waves carry enough energy to heat the solar atmospheric plasma (e.g., Jess et al. 2009, Srivastava et al. 2018). In particular, solar magnetic flux-tubes may act as guidelines for Alfvén waves, which were theoretically predicted by Alfvén (1942), and have been potentially observed in the solar atmosphere (e.g., Tomczyk et al. 2007; Srivastava et al. 2017). The propagation of linear Alfvén waves in the isothermal solar atmosphere was investigated numerically and analytically and cut-off frequencies were revealed by Perera et al. (2015).

As the photospheric and chromospheric plasma are only partially ionized, neutrals can play an important role and affect wave propagation there (e.g., Zaqarashvili et al. 2011). The ion–neutral collisions can lead, among other things, to wave damping (e.g., Piddington 1956; Watanabe 1961; Kulsrud & Pearce 1969; Haerendel 1992; De Pontieu & Haerendel 1998; James & Erdélyi 2002; Erdélyi & James 2004; Khodachenko et al. 2004; Forteza et al. 2007). Moreover, the recent works on two-fluid linear and non-

linear Alfvén waves in the solar atmosphere revealed a rise of the plasma temperature resulting from collisional heating (Martinez-Gómez et al. 2018, Kuřma et al. 2020). Moreover, Murawski et al. (2020) demonstrated that ion-neutral collisions may solve the wave heating problem of a quiet region of the chromosphere.

The main goal of the present paper is to determine how plasma motions at the photospheric level interact with magnetic flux tubes of concentrated magnetic field of a few hundred Gauss strength that reside in inter-network regions. Such motions may be associated with solar granulation. We want to examine how two-fluid effects affect the propagation and attenuation of excited Alfvén waves and compare our 3D results with earlier 2.5D findings (Kuřma et al. 2020).

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we present the two-fluid equations for ions + electrons and neutrals. In Section 3, we describe the 3D magneto-hydrostatic model of a partially-ionized solar atmosphere and present results of numerical simulations. Finally, we outline the summary and conclusions of the present work in Section 4.

2. Two-fluid plasma model

To model the lower atmospheric layers of the Sun, we consider a gravitationally stratified and magnetically confined plasma that consists of two components: ionized fluid (ions + electrons) and neutral fluid (neutrals) that interact via ion-neutral collisions. Ionization and recombination effects are not considered in the present model. This model is governed by the equations describing mass conservation:

$$\frac{\partial \varrho_n}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\varrho_n \mathbf{V}_n) = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \varrho_i}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\varrho_i \mathbf{V}_i) = 0; \quad (2)$$

the momentum equations:

$$\varrho_n \frac{\partial \mathbf{V}_n}{\partial t} + \varrho_n (\mathbf{V}_n \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{V}_n = -\nabla p_n + \varrho_n \mathbf{g} - \alpha_{in} (\mathbf{V}_n - \mathbf{V}_i), \quad (3)$$

$$\varrho_i \frac{\partial \mathbf{V}_i}{\partial t} + \varrho_i (\mathbf{V}_i \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{V}_i = -\nabla p_i + \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{B} + \varrho_i \mathbf{g} + \alpha_{in} (\mathbf{V}_n - \mathbf{V}_i); \quad (4)$$

and the energy equations:

$$\frac{\partial E_n}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot ((E_n + p_n)\mathbf{V}_n) = Q_n + (\varrho_n \mathbf{g} - \alpha_{in}(\mathbf{V}_n - \mathbf{V}_i)) \cdot \mathbf{V}_n, \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial E_i}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \left[\left(E_i + p_i + \frac{\mathbf{B}^2}{2\mu} \right) \mathbf{V}_i - \frac{\mathbf{B}}{\mu} (\mathbf{V}_i \cdot \mathbf{B}) \right] = Q_i + (\varrho_i \mathbf{g} + \alpha_{in}(\mathbf{V}_n - \mathbf{V}_i)) \cdot \mathbf{V}_i; \quad (6)$$

which are supplemented by induction equation and the solenoidal condition:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times (\mathbf{V}_i \times \mathbf{B}), \quad \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0. \quad (7)$$

Here,

$$E_n = \frac{p_n}{\gamma - 1} + \frac{1}{2} \varrho_n |\mathbf{V}_n|^2, \quad \text{and} \quad E_i = \frac{p_i}{\gamma - 1} + \frac{1}{2} \varrho_i |\mathbf{V}_i|^2 + \frac{|\mathbf{B}|^2}{2\mu}, \quad (8)$$

denote the total energy densities of respectively neutrals and ions, while ϱ_n (ϱ_i) is the mass density of neutrals (ions), \mathbf{V}_n (\mathbf{V}_i) the velocity of neutrals (ions), p_n (p_i) the neutral (ion and electron) gas pressure, an \mathbf{B} denotes the magnetic field. The constant μ is the magnetic permeability of the medium, T_i (T_n) denotes the ion (neutral) temperature, $\gamma = 5/3$ the adiabatic index, and $\mathbf{g} = [0, -g, 0]$ is the vector of gravitational acceleration with its magnitude $g = 274.78 \text{ m s}^{-2}$, acting towards negative y -axis in the Cartesian coordinate system we consider.

Note, that we take into account hydrogen as the main plasma constituent with the influence of heavier elements modelled by the use of the OPAL repository of solar abundances (e.g., Vögler et al. 2005). We use $\mu_i = 0.58$ and $\mu_n = 1.21$ being the mean masses of respectively electrons + ions and neutrals. Both above-described fluids interact via ion-neutral collisions. The effect of the interaction between these fluids depends on the ion-neutral friction coefficient

$$\alpha_{in} = \frac{4}{3} \frac{\sigma_{in} \varrho_i \varrho_n}{m_H (\mu_i + \mu_n)} \sqrt{\frac{8k_B}{\pi m_H} \left(\frac{T_i}{\mu_i} + \frac{T_n}{\mu_n} \right)}. \quad (9)$$

Here, m_H corresponds to the hydrogen mass, k_B is Boltzmann's constant, and σ_{in} is the ion-neutral collision cross-section taken as a quantum value (Vranjes & Krstić 2013). Note, that the frictional interaction between these fluids results in additional heat production and exchange terms proportional respectively to the square of the velocity difference and the temperature difference (Ballester et al. 2018 and references

therein):

$$Q_n = \alpha_{in} \left[\frac{1}{2} |\mathbf{V}_i - \mathbf{V}_n|^2 - \frac{3}{2} \frac{k_B}{m_H(\mu_i + \mu_n)} (T_n - T_i) \right], \quad (10)$$

$$Q_i = \alpha_{in} \left[\frac{1}{2} |\mathbf{V}_i - \mathbf{V}_n|^2 - \frac{3}{2} \frac{k_B}{m_H(\mu_i + \mu_n)} (T_i - T_n) \right]. \quad (11)$$

Note that frictional heating is a purely two-fluid effect and its impact on partially-ionized plasma behaviour and contribution to overall heating cannot be studied with the use of single-fluid MHD models.

3. Hydrostatic equilibrium model of the solar atmosphere

In our model, the solar atmosphere is assumed to be initially in a hydrostatic ($\mathbf{V}_{i,n} = \mathbf{0}$) equilibrium. From the ideal gas laws for both neutrals and ions:

$$p_n = \frac{k_B}{m_H \mu_n} \varrho_n T_n, \quad \text{and} \quad p_i = \frac{k_B}{m_H \mu_i} \varrho_i T_i, \quad (12)$$

and from the hydrostatic ($-\nabla p_{i,n} + \varrho_{i,n} \mathbf{g} = \mathbf{0}$) equations, we derive the equilibrium gas pressures:

$$p_n(y) = p_{0n} \exp \left[- \int_{y_{\text{ref}}}^y \frac{dy}{\Lambda_n(y)} \right], \quad (13)$$

$$p_i(y) = p_{0i} \exp \left[- \int_{y_{\text{ref}}}^y \frac{dy}{\Lambda_i(y)} \right]. \quad (14)$$

Here, p_{0n} (p_{0i}) corresponds to the neutral (ion) pressure at the reference level $y_{\text{ref}} = 50$ Mm, and

$$\Lambda_n = \frac{k_B T(y)}{m_H \mu_n g}, \quad \text{and} \quad \Lambda_i = \frac{k_B T(y)}{m_H \mu_i g} \quad (15)$$

are respectively the neutral and ion pressure scale-heights.

In the above described equilibrium model, we implement a current-free, and thus force-free, magnetic field with the configuration of a magnetic flux-tube. This structure in 3D Cartesian coordinates is described as (Low 1985)

$$[B_x, B_y, B_z] = \frac{S[-3x(y-a), x^2 - 2(y-a)^2 + z^2, -3(y-a)z]}{(x^2 + (y-a)^2 + z^2)^{5/2}} + [0, B_v, 0], \quad (16)$$

where a is the vertical location of the singularity in the magnetic field, S is a free parameter corresponding to the magnetic field strength and $B_v = 10$ G is additional vertical component of magnetic field. As a result, the described magnetic structure mimics a photospheric magnetic flux-tube with a magnetic field

strength of $B = 850$ G at its foot-point, extending up into the corona, and attaining a magnetic field strength of $B = 10$ G at $y = 5$ Mm, with magnetic lines becoming almost vertical there (Fig. 1, left). The spatial profile of the corresponding Alfvén speed, $c_A(x, y) = B / \sqrt{\mu(\varrho_i + \varrho_n)}$, is illustrated in Fig. 1 (right). In the upper photosphere and the lower chromosphere c_A attains values lower than 10 km s^{-1} along the flux-tube center, given by $x = 0$ up to $y \approx 0.6$ Mm. Higher-up, as a result of the low total ion+neutral mass density, c_A rises to values above 40 km s^{-1} until the transition region, where it experiences a sudden growth to values close to 900 km s^{-1} .

4. Numerical simulations of 3D Alfvén waves

To solve the two-fluid equations numerically, we use the JOANNA code (Wójcik et al. 2017). In our problem, we set the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy number equal to 0.3 and choose the TVDLF approximate Riemann solver (Toro et al. 2009). We set the simulation box in (x, y, z) as $(-1.28, 1.28) \text{ Mm} \times (0, 60) \text{ Mm} \times (-1.28, 1.28) \text{ Mm}$, where $y = 0$ Mm corresponds to the bottom of the photosphere. In the numerical simulations, we use a uniform grid within the region below the level given by $y = 2.56$ Mm. This region is covered by $256 \times 256 \times 256$ grid points, which leads to a spatial resolution of 10 km there. Above this region, i.e. in the corona, we implement a stretched grid along the y -direction, which is divided into 128 cells whose sizes grow with increasing y . At the top, bottom, and sides, we set all the plasma quantities equal to their equilibrium values.

To excite Alfvén waves, we set the periodic driver in the azimuthal component of ion and neutral velocities, written in Cartesian coordinates as

$$[V_{ix}, V_{iy}, V_{iz}] = [V_{nx}, V_{ny}, V_{nz}] = A_V [-z, 0, x] \exp\left(-\frac{(x - x_d)^2 + z^2}{w^2}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{P_d} t\right), \quad (17)$$

where $A_V = 5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ is the relative amplitude, $w = 0.1$ Mm the width, x_d horizontal position and P_d period of the driver which we set equal to 30 s. This choice results in the effective amplitude 0.3 km s^{-1} of the driver.

Figure 2 illustrates the spatial profile of the θ -component of the ion velocity, $V_{i\theta}(r, y, t)$, with $r = \sqrt{x^2 + z^2}$, at three instants of time, namely at $t = 980$ s, $t = 990$ s and $t = 1000$ s (from left to right) for

Fig. 1. Left: The equilibrium magnetic field lines and ion mas density, $\rho_i(y)$. Magnetic field strength and ρ_i are expressed in Gauss and 10^{-18} g cm $^{-3}$, respectively. Right: The equilibrium spatial profile of Alfvén speed, c_A , expressed in km s $^{-1}$. Here, $r = \sqrt{x^2 + z^2}$.

$P_d = 30$ s, $A_V = 5$ km s $^{-1}$ and $w = 100$ km. It can be seen that the driver excites transversal Alfvén waves propagating along the expanding solar magnetic-flux tube. These waves are strongly damped in the upper photosphere ($0 < y < 0.3$ Mm). Higher up, in the chromosphere, this damping is less significant due to the decreasing ion and neutral densities. The exponential growth of the amplitude with the distance at a rate equal to the pressure-scale height (e.g., Kuźma et al. 2018) becomes dominant above the transition region. At the chromospheric altitudes, the coupling between ions and neutrals is already weaker, thus neutrals do not follow exactly the same evolution as the ions and ion-neutral drift starts playing a significant role

Fig. 2. Spatial profiles of the θ -component of the ion velocity, $V_{i\theta}(r, y)$, with $r = \sqrt{x^2 + z^2}$, at $t = 980$ s, $t = 990$ s, and $t = 1000$ s (from left to right) expressed in units of 1 km s^{-1} . The case of the driving period $P_d = 30$ s, amplitude $A_V = 0.3 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and width $w = 100$ km.

in plasma heating (not shown). In comparison to recent work on two-fluid Alfvén waves (e.g., Kuřma et al. 2020), the damping mechanism shown here is less efficient than its simplified 2.5D counterpart. This fact has a two-fold effect on the overall picture. First, less energy is thermalized in the photosphere, and second, more energy can be transferred to the upper layers and contribute to the plasma heating there.

The top panels of Fig. 3 show time-distance plots of the transversal component of the ion velocity, $V_{i\theta}(r = 0.1 \text{ Mm})$ (left) and the corresponding transversal ion-neutral plasma drift $\log |V_{i\theta} - V_{n\theta}|(r = 0.1 \text{ Mm})$ (left). We can see that, however strongly transversal Alfvén waves are damped in the photosphere, they partially propagate higher up, ultimately reaching the transition region and corona above (compare with Fig. 2). Although Alfvén waves are present in the solar corona, frictional heating cannot

Fig. 3. Time-distance plots of $V_{i\theta}(r = 0.1 \text{ Mm})$, $\log|V_{i\theta} - V_{n\theta}|(r = 0.1 \text{ Mm})$, $\log|V_i - V_n|(r = 0.1 \text{ Mm})$, and $\delta T_i(r = 0.1 \text{ Mm})$ (from top-left to bottom-right).

contribute effectively to coronal heating due to the low abundance of neutrals, as the plasma become essentially fully-ionized there.

Figure 3 (bottom-left) illustrates the overall plasma drift, $\log|V_i - V_n|(r = 0.1 \text{ Mm})$ with all velocity components taken into account. We infer that this drift is larger than the purely transversal drift (Fig. 3 top-right) by a factor of 2. The frictional plasma heating related to magneto-acoustic waves is dominant in the chromosphere, while transversal Alfvén waves contribute to heating partially only, mostly in the upper chromosphere and right below the transition region. Indeed, the right panel of Fig. 3 reveals the corresponding relative plasma temperature, δT_i . The latter shares many similarities to the heating pattern

of acoustic waves driven in the photosphere (Kuźma et al. 2019) and to the heating pattern of 2.5D Alfvén waves (Kuźma et al. 2020).

Note a significant change in the 3D picture of chromospheric heating in comparison to earlier 2.5D results of Kuźma et al. (2020). As the damping of torsional Alfvén waves in the photosphere is weaker, more energy is transferred along the flux-tube by magneto-acoustic waves driven through ponderomotive force. It was already shown (e.g. Kuźma et al. 2018) that due to ion-neutral drift such waves can potentially heat the solar chromosphere. We found that in this process the chromospheric plasma temperature is rising up to a few thousand Kelvin above its hydrostatic value on timescales of a few hundreds seconds. Moreover, the increase of the plasma temperature in the 3D case is one order of magnitude larger than in 2.5D simulations.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we studied the propagation, attenuation and dissipation of torsional Alfvén waves in the partially-ionized lower solar atmosphere. In the framework of our model we described, with use of two-fluid equations, a partially-ionized plasma that consists of ions and neutrals, and we implemented a current-free magnetic field configuration of a magnetic flux-tube. Finally, we generated monochromatic Alfvén waves that originate in the photosphere and followed their evolution.

We found that the generated torsional Alfvén waves are propagating upwards along the magnetic field lines of the solar flux-tube. Although they are strongly damped in the photosphere due to ion-neutral collisions, this damping is significantly weaker than the one revealed in earlier 2.5D studies (Kuźma et al. 2020). More energy is transferred along the flux-tube by magneto-acoustic waves driven through the ponderomotive force. This energy is thermalized in the chromosphere, where the ion-neutral drift is the largest. We found that in this process the chromospheric plasma temperature is significantly rising on timescales of few hundreds seconds. We infer that torsional Alfvén waves are able to indirectly heat the solar chromosphere.

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